

Gap Formation and Resin Flow in Bent Preforms for Resin Transfer Moulding

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Manufacture of composite components employing Resin Transfer Moulding

Localised reinforcement compression at bends in component

→ formation of gaps between reinforcement and tool surface

Experiment: Perspex tool, 90° bend

Observation:

Local effect on flow front propagation; racetracking makes process hard to control

Koutsonas, Spiridon (2015) Race-track modelling and variability in RTM for advanced composites structures. PhD thesis, University of Nottingham.

Gap formation

geometry parameters: φ, r, T (and L)

material parameters: μ, a, b

tool closing force: $\underline{2F_c}$

tool closing force:

$$\underline{F_c} = \frac{F_0(T, a, b)}{\cos(\varphi/2)}$$

tensile force:

$$\underline{F_t} = \mu \underline{F_c} \cos(\varphi/2)$$

normal force:

$$\underline{F_n(\delta)} \quad \text{model?}$$

local pressure:

$$p = \frac{dF_n}{dA}$$

reinforcement compressibility: $t(\delta) = a \left(\frac{p(\delta)}{10^5 \text{ Pa}} \right)^{-b}$

Describe gap in terms of

- Minimum reinforcement thickness (at $\delta = 0$), t_{min}
- Opening half angle (at $t = T$), δ_T

Gap formation (experiments)

Three points on reinforcement surface are known:

$$\delta = \pm\delta_T, t = T \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = 0, t = t_{min}$$

Describe surface as circle,

- with radius

$$R = \frac{2(r+T)(r+t_{min})\cos\delta_T - (r+T)^2 - (r+t_{min})^2}{2((r+T)\cos\delta_T - (r+t_{min}))}$$

- and offset (of centre point)

$$x_c = \frac{(r+T)^2 - (r+t_{min})^2}{2((r+T)\cos\delta_T - (r+t_{min}))}$$

Experimental data suggest that this is a reasonable description

Effective permeability (analytical)

For axial flow in gap, solve Poisson equation

$$C = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2}$$

$$C = \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\Delta p}{L}$$

Special case: “moon shaped” duct

$$x_c = -(r+T) \quad \text{and} \quad R = 2r+T+t_{min}$$

$$\delta_T = a \cos \frac{(r+t_{min})^2 - (r+T)^2 + 2(r+T)(r+t_{min})}{2(r+T)^2}$$

Analogy to torsion of bars (Timoshenko)

$$u(\rho, \theta)$$

$$= C \frac{1}{4} \rho^2 - C \frac{r+T}{2} \rho \cos \theta + C \frac{(r+T)R^2}{2} \frac{1}{\rho} \cos \theta - C \frac{R^2}{4}$$

Calculate

$$Q = \int_{-\theta_T}^{\theta_T} \int_R^{2(r+T)\cos\theta} u \rho d\rho d\theta \quad \text{and} \quad A = \int_{-\theta_T}^{\theta_T} \int_R^{2(r+T)\cos\theta} \rho d\rho d\theta$$

$$K_g = -\frac{Q}{CA}$$

$r+T = 5.0 \text{ mm}$, $R = 9.5 \text{ mm}$

Gap only: $K_g = 1.41 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$

Effective permeability (analytical)

Parameter study

From Darcy-Weisbach

$$K_g = \frac{2 D_h^2}{c}$$

Hydraulic diameter

$$D_h = \frac{4 A_g}{P_g}$$

← gap cross-sectional area
← perimeter

Shape factor, c

- is a measure for the effect of viscous friction on flux;
- is related to the length of boundaries between fluid layers moving at different velocity in laminar flow.

Effective permeability (numerical)

Validation of steady-state CFD simulation (axial flow in moon shaped gap)

Flow velocity distribution

Fine
discretisation
required

Numerical (Ansys CFX)

➔ $K_g = 1.44 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$

Analytical

➔ $K_g = 1.41 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2$

Effective permeability

Effective permeability (simulation)

Analyse axial and transverse flow through bend using CFD

Reinforcement on both sides of bend: porous medium with uniform properties (thickness T)

Compressed reinforcement ($-\delta_T < \delta < \delta_T$): porous medium with varying properties (thickness $t(\delta)$)

In gap: fluid only

Effective permeability (simulation)

Steady-state flow simulation (saturated flow)

φ	r / mm	T / mm	t_{min} / mm	δ_T	R / mm	x_c / mm
90°	3.20	2.80	2.40	42°	7.60	-2.00

Determine permeability from mass flow

axial $K_a = 5.03 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$

transverse $K_t = 9.37 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$

Permeability of flat reinforcement at thickness T is $8.01 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$

Effective permeability (simulation)

Effect of bend angle

(preliminary) estimate for gap shape

simulation models

effective permeability

Effective permeability (simulation)

Effect of (normalised) tensile force
(preliminary) estimate for gap shape

simulation models

effective permeability

Flow front shapes

Transient flow simulation (unsaturated flow)

axial

transverse

Inside of bend: lagging of flow front (locally reduced reinforcement permeability)

Outside of bend: racetracking in gap

- A model for formation of gap between reinforcement and upper tool surface (and the shape of the gap) still needs to be formulated.
- Descriptors for the gap size were defined, i.e. gap height and opening angle.
- An analytical solution for the effective gap permeability was derived for a special case.
- The effect of different parameters on the gap size was estimated.
- CFD simulations were run to find effective permeabilities of the bend (gap and compressed reinforcement).
- Typical flow patterns at the bend were predicted.

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